

UNVEILING THE VOICES OF TRUTH: UNDERSTANDING STUDENTS' EXPERIENCES IN LEARNING THE LIFE AND WORKS OF RIZAL

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 24

Issue 10

Pages: 1127-1144

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2328

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13712829

Manuscript Accepted: 07-22-2024

Unveiling the Voices of Truth: Understanding Students' Experiences in Learning the Life and Works of Rizal

Claire June Z. Quiñanola,* Nathalie Jean T. Templado, Ritchel Marie B. Sabanal, Gliecel D. Ugbamen, Sharlette Mae R. Ditan, Ranie Rose F. Gabutero, Lalyn M. Amolo, Krizamaine Y. Domugho, Jelly Mañen G. Osorio, Jacky Lou V. Medillo, Riscelle A. Mirafuentes, Glaiza Jane R. Magallanes, Jerame E. Landiza, Justine Serato, Jolimar S. Sy, Cyril A. Cabello
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

There are different factors and reasons why a subject is treated as the students' weakness or a very challenging one especially when its nature is boring or not in line with the students' interest. This study described the experiences of the learners and teachers experiences in the subject "The Works and Life of Jose Rizal" at Cebu Technological University – Moalboal Campus, Cebu Province for the school year 2023 – 2024. This study used the Husserl Phenomenology. The sampling design utilized in this study was purposive sampling following established inclusion criteria to identify the participants of the study. 13 participants volunteered to be part of the study. This study used Braun and Clarke's Thematic Analysis to analyze the experiences of the participants. There are three emerging themes that this research generated. These are the (1) Symbol of Filipino Nationalism, (2) Struggle of Bridging Past and Present in Education, and (3) Strategic Instruction for Effective Learning. These themes are pertinent in understanding what is happening inside a classroom where teachers and students share their experiences in learning and appreciating the Life and Works of Rizal. It is highly recommended to encourage teachers to explore different strategies and methods in teaching the subject to make it more engaging and absorbing.

Keywords: *Life and Works of Rizal, experiences, husserl phenomenology, history, thematic analysis*

Introduction

One of the responsibilities of the citizens is to acknowledge, recognize, and study the history of their own country. This history encompasses epic stories that play an unchanging prominence until today and one of the best examples is the Life and Works of Rizal. However, nowadays, this mere responsibility of looking back to the past is dismissed, neglected, and unrecognized. This is one of the biggest lapses that the Philippines is currently facing. However, the government somehow saw this issue and wanted to address it by mandating every Philippine School to offer a Life and Works of Rizal subject under the Republic Act 1425. Thus, when the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) complied with the Rizal Law to make its way into the college curriculum, it revolutionized the ways of the college institution to resurface Rizal's exemplary works to the college students. In some sense, it was called to have "awakened Rizal from his deathbed". This curriculum reconstruction may have maximized the time allotment for the Life and Works of Rizal but was almost given less importance than any major or minor subjects.

Dr. Jose Rizal is a prominent hero in the country's history, marking the struggles and his fight for independence against colonial rule. However, learning to connect with his works and life may be challenging for many students as it is often seen as uninteresting. This is explained by some reasons such as instruction in this subject only focuses on rote memorization and factual recall. The learners tend to undervalue this subject and lack motivation because of how it is conveyed. It was mentioned by Decenilla et al. (2022), that many researchers showed an idea that there is no development in the students learning since the traditional way of teaching history is still present up to this day. And that traditional approach may unwillingly disengage students from historical events, requiring innovative teaching methodologies. In the same sense, Utomo (2020) stated that teaching and learning history is only used as an empty routine, meaningless, and can give students a negative view of history lessons, as boring and less interesting. However, this is undoubtedly an incorrect perspective, one that should be focused on the idea that history's lessons are crucial to the survival of the state and country. Over time, people may accept errors in all their forms and try to learn from them (Laela & Sudrajat, 2020).

With regard to this, several debates arise about why students feel a monotonous environment when learning history. Thus, the teachers and the school must address this issue since according to Alic and Bual (2021), Philippine history is a crucial notion that needs utmost attention, and higher education is now concerned with changing the curriculum that is best fit to defining the methodologies and strategies of history teachers. It was supported by Sumyadi et al. (2020) who deliberated that to achieve the objectives of history lessons, teachers must work in tandem with students to foster their enthusiasm for learning in addition to collaborating with them. Other than that, teachers should also consider essential observations on students' behaviors and attitudes toward learning their historical subjects to support their learning experiences. Thus, research on the experiences of the students inside a history class is given attention and perceived as relevant to tailoring constructive ideas on understanding the reasons behind students' personal experiences in interacting with historical events, much to Rizal's life. As to what Afrina et al. (2021) discussed, the challenging part of teaching and learning history is the fact that people learn to accept their identity through a gradual synthesis of these perspectives and not on the mere recall of historical dates and events. It is the way learners realize their beginnings. To that, historical consciousness can be converted to

consciousness to daily life which students can acquire in learning to meaningfully engage with the subject.

In light of this, the field of education must reconsider how the Life and Works of Rizal should be taught because directly presenting factual information is not enough. Teaching this subject may require more effort and thorough analysis of how it should be done to touch the lives of every learner. The approaches and techniques teachers employ in teaching history nowadays are different from those they employ in teaching other subjects. Thus, choosing the appropriate approaches and strategies to use in history instruction should consider both the content and characteristics of the subject as well as students' needs and interests. Also, it was determined in the study that the majority of history teachers lack adequate knowledge of the topics since they did not take an undergraduate course in the subject. As a result, most of the students are unmotivated and indifferent towards learning the subject. As supported by Lesh (2023), students' historical understanding is poor since instruction primarily consists of lectures and rote memorization. In other words, students do not retain and enjoy learning history. Thus, there should be a change in the way teachers impart knowledge. Students should be actively involved in their education, where they're encouraged to ask questions and gather information to develop historical interpretations. Simply put, if students become actual historians rather than passive learners, studying the stories of the past would be a fun and challenging experience.

There may be myriad studies that present the multidimensional understanding of students' recounts on studying the historical context of a nation, but it is significant to critically assess that these studies can also be a good support for exploring different points of view about what Dr. Jose Rizal has gone through in freeing the nation. The story about his dignified and heroic journey may ensure to target the significant learning competencies, but it should be noted for future readers that this is the genuine nature of the subject, and it doesn't mean invalidating students' views on it immediately without proper examination. That is why in the idea of incorporating this study as a portal to students' voices, educators can bring empathy and focus to improving history lessons and view their students as the center of their instruction in a more comprehensive way while maintaining the goal of teaching history.

This study would like to shed light on the repressed reality of student's feigned interest in the subject and provide valuable insights into how people, most especially teachers, address students' behavior toward achieving a common goal. In essence, the main goal is to re-evaluate students' individual experiences in learning history whether it is caused by some factors that can be identified in the school environment or caused mainly by a more serious matter.

Research Questions

This study described the experiences of the learners and teachers experiences in the subject "The Works and Life of Jose Rizal" at Cebu Technological University – Moalboal Campus, Cebu Province for the school year 2023 – 2024. Specifically, this study answered the following questions:

1. What are the experiences of the teachers in teaching the subject and the learners' learning experiences toward the subject?
2. What are the difficulties they encountered inside the classroom?
3. What are the milestones of the participants when they study the Life and Works of Rizal?
4. What are the participants' coping strategies in teaching and learning the Life and Works of Rizal?

Literature Review

In the pursuit of this study, articles that talk about the endeavors that students went through in a history class, particularly in the Life and Works of Dr. Jose Rizal are being sought. There is a crucial thought in highlighting these articles since they uplift the idea that the subject is, indeed, relevant but somehow misunderstood in various classrooms throughout the 21st century in some cases. Aligned with this, these articles underwent a meticulous evaluation of the statements used that will result in connecting the previous findings of the experiences of students in learning the subject up to the present ones. One factor in finding out about learning Life and Works of Rizal is the capability of this subject to affect students' perceptions—the ability to understand the role of Rizal's works and develop an appreciation of his journey as a great contributor to the Philippines' freedom. These literature and studies help future researchers and readers to ponder on ways to appreciate the topic and Philippine History in general. In addition, the study desires to bring readers to the crucial voices of the people who Rizal once called the hope of our nation—the young generation, particularly the students. Critically, this study guides their way to perceive the Life and Works of Rizal as an existing subject that, like any other subject, needs attention. Moreover, this study marks a way for the future development of the conditions involved and so on.

According to Solé (2019), students have the innate curiosity to question things based on the lessons that they encounter. Thus, displaying moods and other expressions are just the determinant for teachers to reconsider their learning pace to take place only when being fixed and redirected. Students' expressions show that they are trying to understand the topic but failed because it was not cultivated properly. The learning momentum is there but it was being suspended. The competencies can be acquired when teachers also know how to guide students in a step-by-step manner (Riconalla et al., 2022). Additionally, the results indicate that while historical thinking and temporal understanding develop gradually, they can be greatly aided and expedited using pedagogies and social studies/history teaching methodologies, or intervention strategies.

Aligned with what Thompson (2021) said in his study, students interested in learning history were acquired due to some factors that may or may not be common to people's knowledge since it was viewed that history is like a stagnant learning area regardless of what

reasons. Thus, such factors are relevant to be examined in a way that can be beneficial to the integration of the history subject and teacher-student relationship in the classroom. Moreover, it was deliberated that these reasons can also be a bridge to understanding how students learn intellectually and hone their capacity in a much-motivated sense. These developments influence the teacher's decision to grapple with students' strengths and adhere to tailoring the instructions that are especially best for creating motivation in learning the history subject. Such an idea, his study also created a view for teachers about why most students disengage themselves in the history subject and how it is aided and understood. Additionally, his study shows that in every student's engagement in the classroom, there will always be a factor that reasons out why the student is participating in the very beginning, and this is what likely happens to learning history where the feeling of being disconnected with the past is rationally normal and explainable.

Aside from that, Murray (2019) also implied that hearing the children's voices is crucial in the classroom setting since it is the focus now that the curriculum shifts together with the 21st century. This teacher's strategy can also help build students' confidence because they are being heard based on their perspectives on the given content. Likewise, it affects the emotional capacity of students to appreciate what they are being taught. This is in a way that they feel more involved in the classroom which leads them to motivate themselves in participating in the discussion. The more they are involved, the more they perform well in class (Murray, 2019).

Students often find learning history pointless with limited importance to the present-day job skills and demands. This implies that teachers need to diversify into modified teaching and learning methods that focus on major skills such as historical thinking, collaboration, historical consciousness, communication, digital skills, and creativity. It is said that history teachers should incorporate interactive strategies, such as the integration of technology in the process of teaching and learning. According to Cabello et al. (2021), integrating gamification to engage students during the learning process is one of the best ways to catch students' interest and attention, avoiding the feeling of boredom. Researchers such as Sebbowa and Ng'ambi (2020) revealed that the Digital Game-Based Learning (videos, video games, and computer games) model fosters history learning with an entertaining experience as opposed to the memorization and recitation of history facts reminiscent in history classrooms.

If it was emphasized that teachers have concrete impacts on students learning, it is reasonable that teachers should know how to link the past to the present more reflectively through comparisons. As Straaten et al. (2019) pointed out, history is an essential topic in creating active citizenship where the past is frequently used to direct present or future actions. A pedagogical method to accomplish this goal will be establishing examples from the past and the present through comparative analysis of human problems that keep on existing (Perez et al., 2022). Findings demonstrate that both students and teachers think that the case comparisons which focus on the present and past of human issues were easy to understand because these topics were addressed separately. However, some students claimed that it was hard to remember details about the specific historical events because these details needed detailed analysis and deep study. Both students and teachers concurred that blending history teachings with the present creates a stronger captivation and understanding. They proposed to merge the case-comparison approach with the kind of history teaching they already practiced. The aspect of whether a case-comparison approach should be employed in future historical research studies is still debated.

Essentially, students' perception of learning history is sometimes considered powerful and influential because the school curriculum is also driven by the learning experiences of each student. This account was supported in the previous study of Cairns and Garrard (2023) where they addressed the different experiences and stands of Australian students in history class. It was highlighted that although the debate about whether history should be included in the new curriculum, the appreciation of the history subject relies mostly on how students accept the smaller and bigger connections of the past, present, and future. It is not just a subject that students are obliged to learn but it is an aspect that students learn to cherish slowly. As to what the study suggested, reflecting on these connections molds the individual minds of students in historical awareness. Oppositely, this is not what happened. Instead, most students find it hard to involve history in their learning prospects since they perceive it as an untimely lesson. That is why their study gave opportunity to students to speak about their struggles in the sense that they believe such experiences will lead a future spotlight for history to resurface and make possible advances to students' curiosities.

Following the student-teacher relationship in the history classroom, Jawawi et al. (2023) proposed some factors that may affect the opinions of the students toward their learning subject. The first one is the rigid implementation of the curriculum. In the study, Brunei secondary students were evaluated and later found out that students who are closely interested in history are being impeded since history subject in Brunei is only given by choice. Oppositely, students who have the least interest in the subject sometimes feel forced to learn history and make an option not to engage with the subject at all. It was, indeed, a challenge for teachers. In the latter part, teachers are brought into question about how they carried out their history topics that led to this arising problem. That's how the second factor takes place which is the teachers' teaching styles. It was stated that teachers' style in teaching history is mostly focused on the 'chalk and talk' methodology that has been widely used for some time now to adhere to the participation of Brunei's curriculum in public examination. They believed that this pushed teachers to create paper and pencil test examinations more than meaningful activities. Lastly, the study also added that history materials or books have a strong English vocabulary to read which also led students to give up on reading the materials. In a short sense, students lack support in their learning due to the reason that constructive progress is impossible to achieve just by reading the materials.

Many believe that history must be taught comprehensively and tactfully because everything that will be tackled here are events and people from the past that require extensive expounding from a wider perspective of social sciences and immense analysis of social

theory that would overwhelm the learners when learning history. Not only that, it will also necessitate that the learners familiarize themselves with and memorize past events (Ando et al., 2022), specifically the dates and years of the events and the names of the people involved, making history subjects unnecessary and uninteresting. Akmal (2022) believed that this perception of youth learners can be aided through an integrative learning approach. The latter aims to explore the possibility of integration through four steps: establishing a purpose, understanding and leveraging disciplinary insights, leveraging integration, and taking a critical stance after a constructive explanation through a systematic literature review of related studies oriented towards history, interdisciplinary, multidisciplinary, and integrative learning. Integrative learning is a potential idea that could enhance the process of encouraging higher-order thinking abilities in history teaching, despite the dearth of empirical research on the subject. Instead of just letting the students memorize and become comfortable with the material, it is crucial to think about using the knowledge they have imparted practically. The purpose of teaching history subjects interactively can be maximized by integrating history in an interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary way. This will pique students' interest and excitement and result in meaningful learning.

When having meaningful learning, refers to the learning that adapts to 21st-century education that is driven by technology. This technology gives birth to the implementation of e-learning on history. It may include good or bad consequences alternately. Good in a way that they are just staying at home listening to the teacher or studying the material that the professor gave them (Abucejo et al., 2022), and they can be able to watch many references to understand the history and bad in a way that they are bored due to slow internet connection, lack of technology tools, can't be able to talk on classmates and there are many applications to be installed in the cell phone that causes to be full storage (Bahinting et al., 2022). For teachers, integrating technology in teaching allows students to be more advanced with the use of gadgets, applications such as Google Classroom, zoom, and e-portfolios are easier ways for learners to learn in e-learning and are more engaging (Gomez et al., 2024; Jaiciten et al., 2023). It can't deny the fact that technology helps both a teacher and a student to make everything easier and faster but having a face-to-face discussion, activities, and demonstration helps students enhance their social skill, communication skills, collaboration, and creativity will help them grow individually and build a good relationship with each other (Jamiludin & Darnawati, 2022).

New technological contributions made their way in improving instructions since history subjects can now be integrated with some advanced platforms. In the study, the researchers intervened with the class of second-year Education students by using customized lecture videos on TikTok about the selected history topic suited for their year level. It was concluded that after five weeks of continuous implementation of the intervention, students display a great understanding and appreciation towards the topic since the way the teacher handles the subject, was made to be enjoyable and ensures that it adapts to the advancements of the new age. Thus, the study implies that students' behavior on history topics can be dependent on the teacher's ways of handling the subject and how they support students' learning. It is, at some point, a common factor in why students feel like history is rigid or not (Decenilla et al., 2022).

Learners can realize the role of this study in a way where they can be also aware of their involvement as creators of development (Dionaldo et al., 2024; Ogang et al., 2022). Learning requires the active participation of students which results in them building their foundation of knowledge through a given contextual information (Binondo et al., 2023). This thought is not only realized to tell students that their opinions on a particular history subject are important, but it also tells them that their views lead the way for schools to have an in-depth focus on the concerns and feelings of their students. As a result, the Life and Works of Rizal will be examined even better due to the reason that articles about Rizal will continue to emerge once such studies come out. Eventually, it will become a relevant topic to argue with.

In a reasonable reflection, what teachers do in the traditional way of teaching history is through merely read the text and discussing the details alone without any intervention. Surely, this strategy is less effective now that there is a paradigm shift. As supported by the works of literature, there is much more to differentiated instruction than in the traditional way, especially when teaching history. It targets some important domains in other subject areas, how much more in teaching the most challenging subject where most students display divided stands. If this study views students as an active source for development through their take on their experiences, then it will also expect a future where education gives an eye for the factors on why and how students behave and learn from those challenges. Most importantly, the findings of this study expect to show data that supports the behaviors and attitudes that will eventually connect to how readers should understand students' experiences on the subject.

Methodology

Research Design

This study used the Husserl Phenomenology. This design is a qualitative study wherein it focuses on the detailed description of the conscious experiences of the participants. This design can delve into the challenges and highlights they experience as they utilize technological tools in delivering classroom instruction.

Respondents

The sampling design utilized in this study was purposive sampling following established inclusion criteria to identify the participants of the study. The participants should be a teacher teaching the subject and a learner learning the subject which is the Life and Works of Rizal. Their experiences in teaching and learning the subject can be very helpful in understanding why this subject is treated as

boring. The participants should be in Cebu Technological University – Moalboal Campus. 13 participants qualified to be part of the study.

Instrument

The main instrument in this study is the researchers, themselves. It is supported by a semi-structured questionnaire which is content validated to explore the consciousness and experiences of the teachers and learners in the subject – The Life and Works of Rizal (Cabello & Bonotan, 2021).

Procedure

The researchers asked permission from the Campus Director and College Dean to gather data. After the permission is secured, they send the letter to all prospects or possible participants of the study to acquire their consent. After that, they scheduled an interview. After the interview, the data gathered were treated using the analysis established in this study.

Data Analysis

In treating and analyzing the gathered data, the researchers opted to use the Braun and Clarke (2006) Thematic Analysis. This analysis is a method for assessing the qualitative data by identifying and reporting themes within the data set. It's valued for its flexibility and accessibility, making it a popular choice for researchers looking to explore patterns of meaning in textual data. The steps in analyzing the data are as follows: (1) Familiarization with the Data; (2) Generating Initial Codes; (3) Searching for Themes; (4) Reviewing Themes; (5) Defining and Naming Themes; and (6) Writing the Report.

Results and Discussion

After the data analysis, there were 3 emerging core themes namely, the Symbol of Filipino Nationalism, the Struggle of Bridging Past and Present in Education, and Strategic Instruction for Effective Learning. These themes are discussed comprehensively with literature to corroborate the words and experiences of the participants.

Theme 1: Symbol of Filipino Nationalism

Rizal is an enigmatic figure and has had a profound impact on Philippine culture. He stands as a powerful symbol of Filipino Nationalism, whose martyrdom and works contribute to opening the eyes to aim for freedom and shaping what the Philippines is today. He shaped the country through his major works which led to molding the nation's identity and pushing for its independence.

The first is the theme Symbol of Filipino Nationalism. Even though Rizal passed away over a century ago, his scathing critiques of corrupt governance, friar control, and the part played by certain Filipinos in the colonial mission are still relevant today. His intellectual legacy encourages Filipinos to address issues such as corruption, poverty, and violence in an informed way. His life and works symbolize and reflect the struggle for freedom, the quest for identity and dignity. However, when learners and teachers are asked how they viewed the subject Life and Works of Rizal, they perceive it in a sense that the discussion of this theme is supported by the words of the participants.

Student-participant 9 said,

"I learned a lot about Rizal's contributions to literature and how this literature presents Philippine culture to most parts of the world."

Participant 9 explained that Rizal's contributions to literature play a significant role in representing Philippine culture to the world. His literary works, specifically *Noli Me Tangere* and *El Filibusterismo* are fundamental in Philippine literature and have molded the Filipino identity and awareness. Rizal effectively conveyed the significance of education in liberating the Philippines from oppression. Throughout his novels, he consistently highlights the importance of education through the characters and institutions depicted. Through the literary works of Jose Rizal, he emphasizes the significant impact of education on reformation and national enlightenment.

Student-participant 1 stated that,

"Yes, I like the subject since it talks about our roots and how Filipinos aim for independence. That is eventually what we experience today,"

Rizal inspires his generation to work toward creating a country where every Filipino can live in complete freedom (Borla, A. 2023). His dedication to the cause of Philippine nationalism and his willingness to sacrifice his own life for it has left a lasting impact on the history and consciousness of the Filipino people. By conversing with one another, we create our reality, interpreting the text and the outside world to comprehend the struggles of decolonization in interpersonal interactions (Espina, T. 2021). Therefore, Rizal's legacy remains a reminder of the importance of facing one's beliefs and independence. His story serves as a beacon of hope and inspiration for all those who continue to fight for independence and justice in their own struggles against oppression and tyranny.

As student-participant 5 mentioned that,

"He has lots of experiences which we can use as a guide for our future and for future generations."

The participant knows how those experiences of Rizal have a big impact not just on the time of fighting for our freedom but also on the future generations which is today. The occurrence of globalization is what the participant is trying to imply the use of guidance of the future, which people slowly forget their national identity. According to Triana and Sari (2023), the decrease in one's love of culture is one of the issues that globalization brings. The experiences and works of Rizal will serve as a guide to love the culture and the nation because they sacrificed their blood and tears for us to be called Filipinos.

Student-participant 6 mentioned that,

“I like the subject, because it talks about the vibrant history of the Philippines, not just the good side but also the negative side on how he was an instrument to free the country.”

This participant's response means that to bridge the past to the present, it is relevant to awaken the interest of the youth in learning the past, value freedom, and acknowledge those heroes who fought for independence. Reviving the vibrant history of the Philippines, allowing students to share their perspective on learning history, specifically the life and works of Rizal and how it impacted their knowledge, understanding, and love of the said subject. Chapman (2020) addresses the prudential lessons from history about what to do (or not) to achieve or avoid a particular outcome.

However, about the statement of student-participant 6, a teacher-participant mentioned that even though there are students who are personally interested in the subject itself,

“...there are students who are really serious about answering or expressing their thoughts like they really learn something out from the discussion and there are some students who are just merely complying with the activity like their opinions are almost not serious.”

From this perspective, it can be decoded that teachers do not just experience positive responses from their learners but also negative ones. While negative responses from learners indicate a lack of intrinsic motivation, they do not necessarily reflect a bad response.

On the contrary, teacher-participant 1 mentioned that

“My experiences were actually fun in which there are many thoughts that were being enlightened and also the magic of expounding the ideas of Rizal to the point that you want to question “where was this all along in my time as a student?”

It implies that the teacher is interested and hooked to the content of the subject makes her realize a lot of things and gives enlightenment to her views of the life and works of Rizal. Through her interest in the subject matter, she can teach and expound on the content of life and the works of Rizal that will inspire the students to learn and apply it in their generation today. According to Kali et al. (2019), students look up to their teachers, which inspires students to learn about the subject, especially when the teacher answers their questions. It strengthens because of the cooperation (Schmidt, 2020) of the students and the teachers, which results in the engagement and inspiration of the students because, after all, the primary participants who are most affected by the ideas, arguments, discussions, and activities of their teachers are the students themselves (Leal-Rodriguez & Albort-Morant, 2019).

It was also supported by teacher-participant 4 when she mentioned that,

“I noticed that they already have grasped some salient nationalistic views through looking at their performances.”

This implies that a teacher has had different observations from her students' performance. This observation is a positive one where when one looks at their performance, one can conclude that they acquire knowledge from the subject. Looking at this statement, it can be concluded that a teacher's influence in building students' interest in the subject positively affects the teaching and learning outcomes. In teaching history, one must have the characteristics and qualities to do so. According to Gultom et al. (2020), teachers must also have basic learning skills to attain learning goals following the curriculum requirements. Because a teacher's quality and understanding are crucial to a student's academic success.

Thus, his legacy continues to influence every generation may it be personally, intellectually, or politically. And this method is still alive today. Moreover, his life may be an enigmatic one, but it continues to influence, inspire, and motivate every Filipino to pursue every goal with dedication and dignity. Through his achievements and contributions, he will continue to exist as the symbol of a true Filipino, a well-known hero in Philippine history.

Theme 2: Struggle of Bridging Past and Present in Education

The second is the struggle of bridging past and present in education. According to Sutton (2020), history is a vital resource for interpreting and constructing contemporary identities. However, teaching history, particularly the life and works of Rizal, has often been perceived as dull and barren. This is not only because of the subject itself but also because of how educators engage their students in understanding these historical contexts. Additionally, rather than giving explicit instruction, educators must enable the students to be immersed in the subject matter to achieve a more meaningful and engaging learning experience (Bartelds et. al., 2020). Thus, in ineffective history instruction, there are various areas to consider in keeping the students involved and motivated in learning. The discussion of this theme is supported by the words of the participants.

Student-participant 1 mentioned that,

“While filming, we reach the upper lands just to film.”

The experiences of the first students were all about the challenges they faced in the production of Noli Me Tangere, which required filming in multiple settings. These challenges may range from transportation difficulties to dealing with weather conditions and ensuring scene continuity. It is mandated that all Philippine schools offer a course on Rizal’s life, works, and writings. The fact that filming is also part of studying the life and works of Rizal because, through this, students will be immersed in the subject and later recognize the significance of studying this course.

Student-participant 9 said that,

“Rote memorization. The need to memorize exact dates, places, and people.”

The experiences of student 9 in learning the life and works of Rizal emphasized the requirement for rote memorization, where they need to remember precise dates, locations, and individuals. This shows a type of learning that prioritizes memorization of facts over comprehensive and in-depth analysis of the subject. Additionally, in the past, memorization was deemed an important method in schools. However, in today’s educational setting, memorization is regarded as useless since it is at the lowest level of the learning process and will only be retained in the minds of the learners for a short time.

Student-participant 5 explained that,

“Bulos kaayo ang subject tungod sa mga project.”

According to student-participant 5, the subject presents significant challenges due to its emphasis on project-based learning. Projects heavily influence students’ overall grades, necessitating their completion and fulfillment of project requirements, whether involving filming or similar tasks. This aligns with the view that project-based learning encourages students to search for solutions, ask questions, debate ideas, design plans, and communicate effectively with others (Choi et al., 2019). Furthermore, this approach establishes a strong connection between students’ active participation in their projects and their academic outcomes (Pedersen & Hoby, 2020).

Student-participant 8 expressed that,

“It took a lot of effort and money to make the activities that are required for us since it is purely performance-based. It’s mentally, financially, and physically exhausting.”

Student-participant 8 described their experience with the subject’s performance-based activities as highly demanding and taxing. They emphasized that completing these activities required significant time, effort, and financial resources. This combination of demands led to considerable mental, physical, and financial strain, negatively impacting their overall well-being. Despite this, sentiment aligns with the perspective of Wu et al. (2021), who argued that learners’ performance should be considered within a social context, a factor often overlooked in traditional assessment methods. Similarly, Koné (2021) believed that evaluating learners’ progress should consider their cooperation. Performance-based assessment (PBA), unlike traditional assessment (TA), focuses not only on the learning outcome but also on the learning process.

Student-participant 10 asserted that,

“It took up a lot of my time and energy since most of the activities are performance-based, especially filming, and I am not really good in that area.”

As student-participant 10 experienced, it was all about the energy and time constraints they faced in meeting the subject’s requirements, particularly filming, for which they felt they were not proficient enough. Aside from the difficulties in doing these tasks, engaging in filming activities that weren’t within their skill sets made the subject even harder for them. However, it was said by Moreno et al. (2020) that real-life simulations with the aid of technology promote the development of student skills and motivation. Therefore, enabling the students to be immersed in the subject through filming will hone their practical skills, such as creativity and innovation.

With regards to the statement of student-participant 10, teacher-participant 3 also asserted that,

“There are still students who perform just fairly or almost poorly because we can’t say that there is a definite instruction for everyone in class. Every student has their own learning style, and those students who didn’t perform well in class probably had trouble in the type of instruction I used on that day and only favored those who excelled.”

The teacher said that in a classroom setting, learners are diverse, so the methods and approaches to be utilized should also be varied. Therefore, the teacher should be flexible enough to accommodate and adapt to what works best for every student to ensure that learning is meaningful and effective. To employ differentiated instruction in the classroom, there should be instructional clarity, adaptive teaching, and flexible grouping to meet students’ individual needs and keep them involved in the learning process.

Student-participant 11 conveyed that,

“The challenges depend on the teacher’s competence in relaying the topics.”

With what student-participant 11 stated, we can infer that the teacher's ability to effectively teach the subject matter plays a vital role in student comprehension and engagement. If the teacher is skilled and competent, students will understand the concepts easily, and they won't feel uninterested. Additionally, it was said by Ayaydin et al. (2020) that in studying history, either students have negative feelings about the subject, or they are neutral about it. Also, most history teachers lack foundational knowledge since they did not take undergraduate or graduate courses and did not often engage in continuous learning to improve their teaching methodologies.

In relation to the statement of student-participant 11, teacher-participant 3 also conveyed that,

"I think challenges emerge when students express their concerns towards the subject. When they approach me, sometimes I find it hard to address their concerns because I think we also have the same rants about the subject. I mean, I don't also like the subject, so how would I answer them if I, myself, am struggling to like the subject too?"

The teacher is having a dilemma addressing the concerns of the students about the subject because they share similar frustrations with it. Since the teacher herself is also struggling to like the subject, meaningful guidance and support aren't provided to maximize student learning. That is why there should be a development and strengthening of teachers' beliefs and skills, so they'll be able to appreciate the subject, enhance their pedagogy, and create active learning activities applicable to effectively teach the topic (Lee, 2019).

Student-participant 13 articulated that,

"I like the Life and Works of Dr. Jose Rizal, but I do not like the fact that it was being made as a subject in the college. There are lots of things that we should focus on, history is already imprinted, and it's up to the students to know his/ her history."

The statement of Student 13 asserted that the subject, Life, and Works of Rizal is significant and valuable. However, they think it shouldn't be made mandatory in college since there are more relevant and practical subjects to be prioritized. They believe that it is already embedded in history, so it should be pursued according to one's interests and initiative. Contrarily, in a knowledge-based society, we expand the realm of what we don't understand as we discover more information. Therefore, learning more about the past, makes us less uninformed.

Concerning the statement of student-participant 13, teacher-participant 3 also articulated that,

"I think my experience is mostly challenging because, to tell you honestly, even if I am the appointed teacher, I, myself, don't like the subject. I also question myself, "Why do I have to learn (re-learn) that subject?"

This personal struggle of the teacher stems from the idea that she, herself, isn't genuinely invested in the subject. As a result, teaching this course becomes extremely difficult for her since she isn't driven and enthusiastic about this subject. Malm (2020) also mentioned that a teacher's professional competence is largely determined by intrinsic motivation. However, due to a heavy workload, professional ambiguity, and a lack of time for scholarly pursuits, teachers fall short of sustaining their pedagogical practice. Thus, to best maintain quality in teacher education, there should be a conscious choice of pedagogical methods, self-cultivation, and ongoing professional development.

Therefore, in studying the life and works of Rizal, many students fall short of seeing its practical relevance because of the subject's challenging requirements. Though teachers gave performance-based activities such as filming, most of the students find it incredibly demanding since it requires not just their time and effort but also a financial commitment. However, students fail to realize that even though studying this course can be quite challenging, these performance-based activities are one way to effectively teach the subject. Kusuma et al. (2020) argued that most students perceived learning history as boring because they could not feel or fully grasp the moments of those historical events. However, if role-playing activities are enforced, it increases student motivation and achievement. Additionally, it is determined that a teacher's pedagogical competence affects student learning outcomes. That is why sufficient knowledge and appreciation of the subject should be taken into consideration. More importantly, teachers should employ appropriate methods and strategies and create tasks that will facilitate an engaging and worthwhile learning experience to successfully connect the past and present in teaching history.

Theme 3: Strategic Instruction for Effective Learning

In the teaching of relevant subjects, particularly in college, students have an initial curiosity about the subject's true nature and relevance in their chosen course. One could question how this subject can help him elevate his performance throughout a math class, one could question how it would boost his eagerness to learn the laws of the Philippines in a political science class and one could question the subject's mere existence in a way that it might be called as "not relevant" at all. Through a wide lens of these perceptions, students will also be able to trace back their instructors' performances about how they are being taught and their relationship with their learning. This is in the sense that college students are perceived to be more inquisitive and logical thinkers. They are not like elementary students who accept instructions without deep comprehension of what they are accepting and just let themselves go with the flow. Thus, college students are different in terms of appreciating and understanding things as they are.

In the light of this study, this notion has formulated and identified three common reasons why the Life and Works of Rizal and history subjects, in general, are viewed as monotonous subjects. The first one is that history subjects rely more on history books rather than making students relate their experiences to history. As observed in most history classes, students usually stand from their seats and re-

read and analyze what the teacher is saying following what is in the book. There is no meaningful engagement at all (Issar, 2021). Second is the history of having an innate rigorous application of mental processing, requiring students to recall facts rather than understand the context (Popa, 2021). Lastly, history is a challenging subject that requires both students and instructors to view themselves as products of their ancestors' beginnings in the various dimensions of life, which is unfortunately, failed to elaborate on in a history class that's why there are some instances that history learning is being avoided or disregarded (McGregor et al., 2021). It's about misconceptions. These common reasons represent some of the students' responses based on what they experience throughout their history learning. Furthermore, they also described some influences that greatly impacted their behaviors and attitudes toward the subject, the Life and Works of Rizal.

As to what student -participant 1 mentioned in the first question,

"Yes, he's effective. He knows how to deliver and discuss".

Students learning capacities can also be predetermined by the teacher's competency or mastery in relaying the topic. As to what most people believe to be irrational sometimes, teachers' intelligence and commitment matter in some contexts. In tertiary institutions, instructors are expected to deliver their utmost mastery in their course subject since they are teaching future students of respectable professions. With their immeasurable guidance, college students are made bolder and wiser in their field. So, in alignment with their skills, one should also be familiar with what they will be teaching to their students. That is why most of the instructions nowadays are multidimensional which means that instructions are made to cater to different intelligences through varied deliverance. May it be project-based, performance-based, technological-based, or through real-life connection. Relatively, there is an aim to reshape students' discipline using history (Thorp & Persson, 2020). This is to heal the wounded history teaching due to the forceful implementation of traditional instruction like merely memorizing historical names or terms. Additionally, Şenşekerci and Sarı (2019) also pointed out the relevance of in-service training for all the instructors who mold future teachers in the education field. This relevance should be the focus of undergraduate instructors to support and attest to education students' readiness in applying their knowledge in teaching tools and methodologies. Above all, it takes one great teacher to give birth to a greater teacher. The view of the first student in the gathered data might be the stepping ground for future teachers to modify their instruction more in a suitable learning preference so that history subjects are more likable and interesting. This is also one of the existing problems of history learning—what to like and unlike about history.

Consequently, student -participant 5 quoted in the interview,

"I don't like the subject itself because the Life and Works of Rizal were written in history already, there is no need for such things such as filming just for the sake of the subject to be recognized by the students. The subject is just a hassle because of the projects."

From the first sentence of the response, it was already very clear that the attitude of the student towards history learning is poor and quite alarming. As to some people who aren't concerned about teaching history as their profession, they can conclude that this statement is shallow and almost valid. However, for some history instructors, this entails a deep unveiling of factors that contribute to such an extent. One that needs to be fixed and aided is the Rizal Law. Rizal is a prominent person in our lives. While examining this statement, it can be retaliated that the student probably feels that way because they are bombarded with project-related tasks and performance-based tasks like filming. This is an implication of the efforts of education nowadays to incorporate interactive activities because they are determined to prevent students from hating history in the future (Kisida et al., 2020). To make learning fun, some of the schools even creatively dramatized the life of Rizal. Thus, there is an application of artistic skills towards students which is, in fact, essential in cultivating appreciation towards the past.

Moreover, such positive consequences are only up to the applied teaching strategy of the instructor continuously just to achieve the needed activities and projects prepared by the curriculum (Malazonia et al., 2021). That explains why students are left with no choice but to learn history whether they like or dislike the subject itself. Oppositely, if the fifth student dislikes the subject because of the projects, some students like the seventh student also want to accept the subject as an Inspirational lesson rather than a negative subject out of personal perspective.

As to what student-participant 7 implied,

"It influenced my perspective about our freedom now since, before, we knew that Rizal rose to take the risk, and he did a lot of things that I think we cannot do now."

In the articulation of the statement, the student has slightly unlocked a new outlook on the nation they live in. It was more about looking at the nation as the fruit of success that Rizal has been longing for a long time. Through that, the student values freedom even more than before because of the subject. There is a character change. An affective domain that most instructors are familiar with since it must be importantly included in the learning objectives. With what Miftakhu Rosyad et al. (2022) presumed in their study, instructors are instilling nationalistic appreciation toward students' characters in the sense that it will enhance and boost their confidence in knowing their antecedents, dominant with Filipino characteristics as their own. Aside from that, knowing and understanding the identity that we believe in, and our identity can be difficult sometimes. Hence, assessments that target character development in history are profoundly crucial for having inspirational and meaningful learning (Hania et al., 2020). Although values integration in history learning

and teaching is still dependent on the values learned by the instructor. If the instructor is equipped with pedagogical knowledge about such integration, then students might as well learn how to use their emotional standpoints on the subject too. Otherwise, the focus would be more likely to decline in that domain and divert focus on cognitive level instead just like how the same participant envisioned a future history class after the question on how they would design an instruction if they were the teacher.

As follows, the student -participant 7 states that,

“If I am the one to teach, I think I will make my students more enhanced in terms of their memory so they can acquire such historical knowledge about Rizal’s life and works.”

From the statement, the student indicates that if they were allowed to teach, they would significantly improve their students’ memory capabilities. This would be particularly beneficial in the context of learning about Rizal’s life and works. By enhancing their memory, students would be able to better understand and remember the historical significance of Rizal’s contributions. This would not only deepen their knowledge of our national hero but also instill a sense of pride and appreciation for our rich history. Various strategies are effective in helping students learn history. One of these strategies is using acronyms, as Salehi et al. (2021) found that using acronyms had a significant effect on improving vocabulary recall among learners. By breaking down complex terms into easily memorable acronyms, students would be better equipped to remember key concepts and historical events. However, this strategy can also be effective when integrated with collaborative learning. As Ashrafzadeh et al. (2023) discovered, Cooperative Learning is one of the most important factors or predictors for learners to achieve learning success. By working together in groups, students would be able to share knowledge, discuss ideas, and engage in meaningful discussions. This interactive learning environment would not only enhance their memory capabilities but also foster a sense of camaraderie and teamwork. Furthermore, these strategies would foster a more engaging and interactive learning environment, encouraging students to actively participate and engage with the material. Ultimately, this would lead to a more comprehensive and meaningful learning experience for students.

In response to questions asked during the interview, student 8 -participant implied,

“I would teach in a way that my students can view educational videos about Rizal and that they can create their own version of the videos too.”

With their significant role in content delivery in flipped, blended, and online learning environments, educational videos have grown in importance within the higher education sector. It is essential to use instructional videos when learning highly visual subjects. According to a recent study, there are significant correlations between advanced students’ digital technology-based learning activities and teachers’ technology-related teaching abilities (Sailer et al., 2021). To help students grasp and see examples, teachers can demonstrate everything in depth. Because students must adapt to the digital environment, they look for novel approaches to learning new subjects. Videos are aesthetically pleasing and accessible on every kind of platform, including tablets, laptops, PCs, and smartphones.

According to Walsh and Henderson (2022), TikTok and YouTube are the most popular social media platforms for short-form video content. Therefore, if they have access to the internet, students across the world can attend video lectures. Teachers can utilize video learning to set aside time and space for active learning because it works well on both sides of the classroom wall. A video may be made once and updated as needed, allowing more classroom time for in-person interactions and live conversations with students. Even better, learners can watch the videos again to review the material to get ready for examinations or tests. Since they are observed via both the auditory/verbal and visual/pictorial processing channels, learners can improve their memory and recall skills by retaining more information and forming more pertinent associations. It accommodates various learning styles as well. They promote reasoning, decision-making, problem-solving, and critical thinking. It also aids in engagingly providing the subject and enables us to view information from numerous perspectives.

Subsequently, student-participant 9 counterclaims,

“I would teach it in a way that my students will have fun while still maintaining the essence of the subject.”

This response insinuates that the student is aware of how the Life and Works of Rizal subject rarely pique their interest. The subject in question deals with the past, emphasizing the various dates, events, characters, and specific details essential to the formation of the Filipino people’s identity today. Therefore, according to student 8, the core of the course, The Life and Works of Rizal, could still be upheld if it is taught in a way that makes learning enjoyable for the students. In keeping with the theme of making learning enjoyable for students, it is evident that gamification of the material would encourage discussion among the pupils. Before the previous discussion, video interventions could be used as a potential instructional tool to make learning history more enjoyable, according to Gheitasi et al. (2023). They stressed the significance of using historical authenticity, historical settings, key components, and the legitimacy of the information incorporated into the game as indicators of the effectiveness of the video game’s implementation in the classroom.

As student-participant 11 asserts,

“I like the subject because of the teacher and how he or she delivers the topic very well in a way that we can understand something.”

Teachers who deliver the topic well, especially when it is driven by their exceptional teaching skills, tend to capture the attention of the students. Deeper understanding and appreciation among the students can be fostered when a teacher can communicate and engage

them with even the most difficult topics. And there is a high possibility that students can respond if given questions. Teachers used various teaching strategies tailored to the diverse needs of the students, fostering an inclusive learning environment where they could thrive. As explained by Papadatou-Pastou et al. (2020), learning styles are still recognized as a virtual truism in education, even though they are a neuromyth. The fact that different theories have been used to define learning styles using entirely different concepts and classifications raises some serious concerns. It was discovered that Gardner's multiple intelligences and the Visual-Auditory-(Reading)-Kinesthetic (VAK/VARK) framework were the primary conceptual frameworks used to define learning styles.

Furthermore, a lot of teachers mistakenly associate learning styles with learning theories (such as behavioral or cognitive theories). To determine the learning styles of the students, the teachers used various techniques, like observation of daily interactions and test administration. Learning styles could be incorporated into the classroom in a variety of ways, such as through exercises, interactive teaching strategies, and teaching aids. According to Munna and Kalam (2021), teaching and learning are the processes of transferring knowledge from teachers to students. It is defined as the process by which a teacher creates teaching materials, establishes the lesson's objectives, and puts the teaching and learning strategy into practice. Role-playing and giving students adequate, helpful formative and developmental feedback greatly increases their self-esteem and confidence as the findings of the study imply. Additionally, it was found that a stimulating learning environment promotes inclusivity and improves academic achievement for both teachers and students. The various strategies, learning styles, and skills of the teachers are critical to the accomplishment of learning objectives. Teachers have a significant impact on how their students and society develop through good communication, building relationships, and a dedication to continuous improvement.

Additionally, the challenge doesn't end there since teachers are meant to deal with both their attitude and that of the students at the same time. Given an example of relating the teacher's own experiences towards the history topic. The teacher in such a case would probably find it hard to transcend the topic towards the current life because he lacks initiation to learn the topic. That is why this study has interviewed teachers in such a way that they can give their own teaching experiences in the subject. This is also to highlight that both students' and teachers' stances are being valued and that every particular response is brought to immense evaluation.

Firstly, teacher -participant 1 revealed that,

"I used some strategies like Think-Pair-Share or usually I group them into 3 or more and then one of them will be called to discuss their assigned topic and what will be the score of that person will be the score of that group."

In the field of education, modern teaching techniques are becoming more and more important, particularly in terms of students' academic and educational progress. When creating a learning plan, it is imperative to consider a range of learning approaches, including models, strategies, techniques, and procedures. For students to comprehend the learning process clearly, modern learning methodologies must be applied in the classroom. One way to teach is through strategic instruction, which demonstrates to students how to take in, retain, and apply the knowledge. Students can apply these strategies for the rest of their lives. To help learners avoid their areas of weakness and instead depend on their areas of competency, instructional strategies are particularly crucial. Therefore, the degree to which students value specific strategies will determine how willing they are to apply such strategies to their homework and classwork. To succeed academically, students must be aware of their unique learning profiles and needs as well as how and why these strategies can support them. Consequently, each student's self-awareness of his or her profile of strengths and weaknesses as well as the techniques that work best for that learning profile is a crucial component of an effective instructional education.

Think-pair-share is a collaborative learning method that involves posing a problem to the class, giving them time to think about it alone, and then having them collaborate in pairs to solve it and present their solutions to the class. This is one example of strategic instruction for effective learning. Through the course of the learning process, sharing and discussing problems with a partner is a great way for teachers to foster critical thinking and communication skills. By using these strategies, teachers can better comprehend the varied learning profiles of their students and establish classroom environments that support the success of each one of them. Learning innovation is the focus of educational service development (Divina et al., 2023). By doing this, learning effectiveness is to be attained, which in turn impacts the quality of graduates. As a result, a learning program's effectiveness largely relies on how well teachers manage learning. The teacher's role is positioned as the front guard that determines the success of the process, even in learning activities (Wuryandani & Herwin, 2021).

As the same teacher-participant elaborates,

"What I did was I modified the instructions through a "chika style" or conversational style so that students can relate to what I say and that they will not forget everything from it because the bottom line is they really listen quite attentively."

Incorporating an engaging use of "chika style" or a conversational teaching style within a classroom setting can boost the learners' interest and understanding. Through conversational teaching, teachers can easily establish teaching strategies that foster a friendly environment in class and make the content more relatable and interactive for students. As Filgona et al. (2020) claimed, teachers should ensure learners feel comfortable in their environment by freely expressing themselves. In the same way, teachers should maintain friendly and approachable language so that learners feel comfortable and ensure that they create an encouraging environment for students, to communicate with their teachers and peers (Monteiro et.al, 2021). Therefore, in the case of teaching Rizal studies, adopting a conversational type of learning procedure should be the best way of making the students feel and experience Rizal's life and work.

This way, teachers could make the subject matter more engaging since students would learn better when they try to look at things from Rizal's perspective by using examples or anecdotes from their own lives.

Aside from that, teacher -participant 2 also said that,

"I use a strategy where I relate the topic towards the current happenings in this world."

As interviewed, the teacher has a different way of teaching the students. It was stated that the teacher uses a real-world relation between the past and the present allowing the students to critically think about how that event in the past correlates to that of the present or the current event. In this way, students might be able to uphold ownership of their learning because this kind of intervention usually requires students to share their thoughts about their own experiences. Relatively, the teachers also share their own experiences. This is an essential form of inquiry where conversational proceedings are happening inside the classroom. As to what most professional teachers believed to be true, having two-way communication inside the classroom improves understanding and enhances motivation towards the students since there is what people call an "emotional nudge". In the findings of Blevins et al. (2020), the use of critical inquiry in history teaching gives way for the topic to be accepted in a way where students can ponder on historical-related things. There is an application of philosophy where students have endless questions about what the teacher is teaching. Hence, it was also identified that the content knowledge of the teacher should be partnered with its pedagogical knowledge. Teachers should also feel what their students are expressing prior to what is being discussed so that they can fix and tackle issues together regarding working and connecting with the dots of history, present, and future. Moreover, several interventions such as the inquiry approach have varied impacts on students learning and that is what teachers should be careful of. One intervention may or may not impact comprehensively on other students because of diverse intellects. Abdugulova et al. (2020) agreed that developing an appropriate approach and reflecting on errors in teaching should be the focus of the teacher to implement better strategies since finding and selecting one is a disturbing task for teachers.

Specifically, the same teacher lays a specific approach that she usually used in the classroom in which the teacher-participant said that,

"Their performances in every after our class are somewhat fine because we have this term called "being constructive". They construct their own learning in a way that even I don't tell them to understand and study this and that, they still really find something that can support their learning such as relating what they have heard from the discussion to that of a social media meme and throwing jokes about it."

In alignment with the "fun learning" this study has tackled in the previous discussion, the second teacher that was being interviewed expressed the essence of using social media platforms to learn or re-learn history in the context that the students have an initial background already of what Rizal did in his life in the form of his great contributions. With this, it is in the power of the teacher to show that previous knowledge will be cultivated. That is why the students, as part of their constructivist approach to their learning, used social media memes in learning to grapple with Rizal's ideologies. Social media memes are jokes circulating on different social media platforms it usually addresses issues today but it's more of entertainment. Some studies believe that entertainment is one of the strong tools for students to retain and remember what they have in mind. Such studies like the study of Suswandari et al. (2021) expressed that history learning and teaching will possibly go beyond its success due to the interactive reformation of the class in the procedures of using entertainment clippings of events and historical accounts. However, such digital intervention entails negative consequences on the historical facts that the teacher might present. It would also be easier for the moderators of the memes to change and add unnecessary claims about historical facts that will later contribute to unethical biases. Consequently, it will be a task for the teachers to reshape this and address these biases in the classroom from time to time to avoid misconceptions because the commitment and consistency to address misconceptions can enhance critical and logical thinking to both teachers and students that will eventually elevate academic performances (Bhat et al., 2023).

Relatively, there is also a hope for aiding these historical misconceptions because as per teacher-participant 4,

"I infused "chismis" or unverified facts about his life which piqued my students' interest."

In the given assertion, the teacher stressed a strategy that is effective both in the context of the Philippines and internationally. *Chismis*, or, in English, gossip, functions as a means of collecting and spreading information that is deemed a rumor due to its unreliability and lack of authenticity. It is crucial to acknowledge that the exchange of information takes place during the discourse, with a focus solely on the act of gossiping and nothing else. Moreover, the concept of gossiping was introduced by Van Ditmarsch et al. (2020), who highlighted gossip as a form of peer-to-peer communication wherein the information shared heavily relies on the specific mode of communication utilized. As this approach is implemented in educational settings, students may find it engaging since teachers adjust the delivery method, thereby enhancing students' engagement. Additionally, Rajačić et al. (2020) engage in a discourse regarding the presence of functionalist, dramaturgical, and social exchange paradigms within the realm of theoretical and empirical investigations on gossip within the discipline of sociology alongside various other social sciences. The maintenance of social cohesiveness within groups, the dissemination of cultural values, sociocultural learning, the establishment of social control, the process of establishing one's social standing and reputation, the social exchange of information, and many other social processes are all acknowledged as being significantly impacted by gossip. Because gossip encourages interactive discussions in the classroom, it can also therefore allow the teachers to fix false rumors.

As to what teacher-participant 4 states,

“The challenges are how to make the classes interesting and stimulating.”

Teacher -participant 4 highlights the value of having an engaging and stimulating classroom environment. Teachers can create a conducive learning environment in the classroom where students are motivated and eager to participate by emphasizing engagement. They understand the difficulties associated with these tasks and that effort and creativity are needed to keep the students' interest. According to Amiruddin et al. (2021), Islamic education teachers' academic communication styles stimulate students' interest in learning about interpersonal communication, which includes approaching, advising, setting an example, and rewarding. Second, group communication entails encouraging and raising students' activity levels, establishing habituation, and providing a gentle, decisive, and attractive explanation of the subject matter. Students who were more engaged in their studies completed their assignments more diligently and hard, which improved their grades. The contributing factors are the support of fellow teachers, the teacher's communication skills, and the student's openness to receiving guidance. Parental support and students' level of understanding and response power are the factors that inhibit them. Affuso et al. (2022) found that teacher support and parental monitoring over time directly and positively affected motivation and self-efficacy, which in turn positively impacted the academic performance of the students. The results also demonstrated that, over time, parental supervision and teacher support had a significant effect on the student's academic performance. Parents influenced students the most in terms of motivation, at the same time in terms of self-efficacy teachers influenced students the most. To improve each student's academic performance, the results highlight the importance of implementing interventions designed to increase teacher support and parental supervision.

In the end, teaching history education is indeed challenging as teachers may or may not be effective in delivering the message of history. Viewing from the perspective of the teachers, students, in some sense, might understand the difficulty of teaching the subject itself. How much more when teaching students like them who need more valuable reasons to learn the subject. In teaching, the top priority will always be the students' concerns and other relevant standpoints. Through this, teachers strive to take on the challenges in teaching history education following searching the endless pit of solutions towards substantial issues in learning the subject, the Life and Works of Rizal.

Conclusions

It is conceivable that the reason why one cannot see the future is that they would be too worried about it. When one can discover what is ahead, one cannot savor the present moment. The same holds for the Life and Works of Dr. Jose Rizal. The world is evolving; it continuously evolves, and people are now embracing the present and freedom that was laid down by various heroes. Significantly, it is not just Rizal's life, works, and writings that learners should be studying but also his values, principles, and ideals. This doesn't only fulfill the obligation to honor his contributions and accomplishments but also allows his influence to serve as a source of hope for the present and generations to come. Through the deliberation of the different responses of both students and teachers, this study concludes that conditions regarding the academic performances of the students in the subject, The Life and Works of Rizal, vary depending on the effectiveness and quality of teaching. Hence, teacher development is the core extent to which the educational constituents need to visualize and plan accordingly in a more systematic manner. More appropriately, the take on having to lay blame on either the students or teachers for their performances in school is quite irrational and incompetent in some sense. Whatever they have acquired in the class is purely based on unfixed gaps and unintentional attitudes towards the subject. This is because people cannot immediately control mishaps in life, and the one that makes a great difference is people's concern to take on the risk and change what must be changed.

The articulation of varied experiences of both the students and teachers has conceived specific exhortations that students, teachers, future researchers, and readers, in general, can ponder on. These selected exhortations aim not just to change the way the subject, Life and Works of Rizal is viewed but also to give a positive outlook for the implementation of history education. How it impacted the school and how it paved the way for creating the future of the society. Reasonably, such recommendations are always a part of every inference. Thus, having to create a great divide between what to and not to remember is relatively essential. To give a sequential array of recommendable thoughts, this study highlights the following:

Rizal in the curriculum doesn't aim to spread his greatness towards the nation but to make people feel the greatness of their own. This quotation has come to fill the gap between feeling the need to study the subject and having to feel the essence itself. In a rational judgment, the subject doesn't exactly tell tertiary students to remember his life but to change their mindset based on his life instead. It hopes to take on a nudge. Making students feel the rightness and wrongness of their every action and decision in life. This study deems that perhaps, students feel the hesitation to go all out on the subject because they think the nature of the subject is just to purely teach them mental processing. Thinking of having to memorize facts is strenuous for sure. In that case, tracing back to this part might be a commendable turn for the constructive conception of the subject.

It takes one great obstacle to change a person's efficacy in doing what they ought to do but oftentimes it pays a fruitful reward. It was found that some students appreciate and enjoy learning about the life and works of Rizal while some have difficulties, especially in terms of the methodologies used by their teachers. Teachers must strive to make the life and work of Rizal easy to understand for students by providing real-life examples and connecting them to contemporary issues. As a result, interactive activities and hands-on exploration should be made to help students understand the significance of Jose Rizal in Philippine history. In addition, teachers must

provide students with opportunities to reflect on the contributions of Rizal and how it has an impact on freeing and making the nation interdependent.

A variety of stories are revealed by exploring in regard to how students encountered learning about the life and work of Rizal. It is made clear by qualitative analysis that studying the course of Rizal is more than just historical education, rather, it is a source and a tool for critical thinking and cultural appreciation. In that case, future researchers must recognize and value the variety of viewpoints and insights that result from these experiences as teachers and students. They can include some factors affecting students' experience to narrow down their different standpoints which can be used to actively participate in creating a more inclusive and enlightened society based on the values upheld by Rizal himself.

Aside from that, empathy and natural curiosity are some of the key components for becoming a great qualitative researcher. The one that understands and motivates participants to fully give their honest perspectives based on the given topic. The one that saturates the truthfulness of their voice makes them empowered and valued. This can be traced back to the reason that this kind of paper has its setbacks students are sometimes afraid to voice out what is in their minds. Always remember that every discussion of opinions is an opportunity for growth, both mentally and emotionally.

A student may or may not be meaningfully involved in the learning process if the teachers themselves act as constructed aliens. As teachers' competence affects student learning outcomes, educators must display utmost dedication and enthusiasm in teaching the subject to be able to employ varied and innovative instructional methodologies that meet the diverse learning styles and interests of the students. This study believes that it should be the first step that teachers need to consider—to develop intrinsic motivation within their selves. The significance of cultivating a profound understanding and appreciation of the subject, *The Life and Works of Rizal*, for both teachers and students should be one of the priorities.

As the field of study continues to broaden, there is growing emphasis on incorporating diverse perspectives and voices into the articles. By incorporating extensive connections brought by this study to that of the other related research, it could be a challenging task for readers to connect dots from each of the works of literature. Thus, this study would be a better wake-up call for them to be rational and unbiased towards different standpoints and assess what to be assessed which can empower them to become fully responsible and ethically conscious individuals in general.

Putting more emphasis on real-world connection in the educational approach should also be included in the priorities of institutions. Since Rizal's ideas are valuable in society, economics, and government phases, students should learn the essence of those ideas in multiple stages of our society and how his ideas contribute to solving modern issues. Highlighting that modern issues can be solved by past occurrences.

This study also suggests readers to explore more and be informed by Rizal's writings, letters, and historical novels to provide them a firsthand option to work hard for their future and follow Rizal's determination to achieve success through working on this literature. This also targets, not just the readers but aspiring literary artists as well. Moreover, learners could connect Rizal's thoughts in his writings to that of their academic performances.

Additionally, visiting significant historical sites associated with Rizal and exploring his scientific, medical, and personal endeavors can provide a more comprehensive view for both students and future researchers to understand their aims and answer their relevant questions about his life. This could boost their individual experiences and check whether a fact is a fact or otherwise.

The research combined the truths of different sides of the story, hearing the voices of the students and teachers on how they view the subject. This quotation has identified the gap between the teaching style in history classes and the subject matter itself. To further prevent the title from being called "the boring subject," integrating modern technology is recommended. This study aims to change teaching strategies, which can be a tool that hopes to value the different viewpoints through interactive discussion, encouraging a student-centered approach, and maintaining a culture of continuous feedback. Making students feel engaged and have a sense of belongingness and offering students the opportunity to connect the lesson to their lives. This recommendation aims to inspire teachers to integrate different types of approaches in teaching so that not only the students learn about Rizal's life itself but also his values that can be applied to the lives of every student. Through such an approach, the legacy of Rizal will continue to inspire future generations.

References

- Abdugulova, B., Kassymov, M., Bissenbayeva, Z. (2020). MODERN TRENDS OF SCHOOL HISTORICAL EDUCATION DEVELOPMENT IN THE REPUBLIC OF KAZAKHSTAN. *PalArch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt / Egyptology*, 17(3), 781-789. <https://doi.org/10.48080/jae.v17i3.171> (Original work published November 3, 2020)
- Abucejo, C. M., Amodia, J. B., Calorin, R., Deo, N. F., Fuentes, M. J., Lamila, K. N., ... & Minyamin, A. (2022). Going Back to Elementary Years: The Parents Lived Experiences in Modular Distance Learning. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 2(6), 477-489.
- Affuso, G., Zannone, A., Esposito, C., Pannone, M., Miranda, M. C., De Angelis, G., Aquilar, S., Dragone, M., & Bacchini, D. (2022). The effects of teacher support, parental monitoring, motivation and self-efficacy on academic performance over time. *European Journal*

of Psychology of Education, 38(1), 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10212-021-00594-6>

Afrina, A., Abbas, E. W., & Susanto, H. (2021). The role of historical science in social Studies learning materials for increasing values of student's nationalism. *The Innovation of Social Studies Journal*, 3(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.20527/iis.v3i1.3769>

Akmal, A. (2022). Integrative Learning in History Education: A Systematic Literature review. *Dinamika Ilmu*, 375–392. <https://doi.org/10.21093/di.v22i2.4792>

Alic, A. K. B., & Bual, J. M. (2021). Readings in Philippine History: Course Review, Best Practices, and Challenges among Higher Education Institutions. *Philippine Social Science Journal (University of Negros Occidental-Recoletos- Online)/Philippine Social Science Journal (University of Negros Occidental-Recoletos-Print)*, 4(4), 91–103. <https://doi.org/10.52006/main.v4i4.424>

Amiruddin, A., Nurdin, N., & Ali, M. (2021). Islamic Education Teacher Communication Strategy in Increasing Students' Learning Interest. *International Journal of Contemporary Islamic Education*, 3(1), 41–61. <https://doi.org/10.24239/ijcieid.vol3.iss1.31>

Ando, K., Basilisco, J., Deniega, A., Gador, K., Geraldo, P. J., Gipulao, W. E. M., ... & Minyamin, A. (2022). Learning without Learning in the New Normal: College Education Students Lived Experiences in Blended Learning Modality. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 2(6), 455-464.

Ayaydın, Y., & Aktaş, V. (2020, December 31). Opinions of Social Studies Teachers regarding Teaching History Topics in Social Studies Lessons. <https://dergipark.org.tr/en/pub/ekvad/issue/59178/851116>

BAHINTING, M. A., Ardiente, M., Endona, J., Herapat, M. A., Lambo, D., Librea, H. J., ... & Minyamin, A. (2022). Stronger than the Internet Connectivity: A Phenomenology. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 2(6), 465-476.

Bartelds, H., Savenije, G. M., & Van Boxtel, C. (2020). Students' and teachers' beliefs about historical empathy in secondary history education. *Theory and Research in Social Education*, 48(4), 529–551. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00933104.2020.1808131>

Bhat, R. M., Rajan, P., & Gamage, L. (2023). Redressing Historical Bias: Exploring the Path to an Accurate Representation of the Past. *Journal of Social Science*, 4(3), 698–705. <https://doi.org/10.46799/jss.v4i3.573>

Binondo, J. M. B., Binondo, J. R., & Cabello, C. (2023). Teachers' Resiliency in Modular-Printed Modality: A Phenomenology. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 14(10), 1180-1188.

Blevins, B., Magill, K., & Salinas, C. (2020). Critical historical inquiry: The intersection of ideological clarity and pedagogical content knowledge. *Journal of Social Studies Research*, 44(1), 35–50. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jssr.2019.09.003>

Borla, A. (2023b). Rizal in the 21st century: the influence of his literary works. *ResearchGate*. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.10889.21601>

Cabello, C. A., & Bonotan, A. M. (2021). Designing and validating an instrument to assess the wellness of business process outsources' customer service associates. *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 9(1), 1-11.

Cabello, C. A., Abadiano, M. N., Mabitad, A., Pulma, D. B., & Hipe, A. (2021). Gamification in Education: The Motivation-Exploration-Implementation Theory. *Turkish Online Journal of Qualitative Inquiry*, 12(7).

Cairns, R., & Garrard, K. A. (2023). 'Learning from history is something that is important for the future': Why Australian students think history matters. *Policy Futures in Education*, 22(3), 369–382. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14782103231177615>

Chapman, A. (2020) 'Learning lessons from the Holocaust: A critical exploration'. In Foster, S. Pearce, A. and Pettigrew, A. (eds), *Holocaust Education: Contemporary challenges and controversies*. London: UCL Press, 50–73. *Holocaust Education*. (2020). In UCL Press eBooks. <https://doi.org/10.14324/111.9781787355699>

Choi, J., Lee, J., & Kim, B. (2019). How does learner-centered education affect teacher self-efficacy? The case of project-based learning in Korea. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 85, 45–57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2019.05.005>

Decenilla, S. A., Apolinario, R. C., Cuaton, Z. T., & Clarido, C. (2022). Improving Student Knowledge on Selected History Topics through Tiktok Platform as Digital Learning Tool. *Journal of Digital Learning and Education/Journal of Digital Learning and Education*, 2(3), 134–149. <https://doi.org/10.52562/jdle.v2i3.410>

Dionaldo, S., Aquino, H., Barrete, A., Celestian, E., & Cabello, C. (2024). The Narratives of Teachers in the Hinterland Schools: Basis for Management Plan. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 21(2), 181-194.

Divina, D. B. ., Miparanum, M. G. D. ., Pondavilla, J. F. ., & Zita, C. T. . (2023). The Impact of Modern Teaching Strategy in Enhancing the Learning Skills of the Grade 9 Students at Holy Rosary College Foundation. *Idarah (Jurnal Pendidikan Dan Kependidikan)*, 7(2), 183–196. <https://doi.org/10.47766/idadrah.v7i2.1912>

Espina, T. (2021b). Ali'e' and Asi'i: Unsettling the Rhetorics of Filipinos on Guahan. *College English*, 84(1), 100–120. <https://doi.org/10.58680/ce202131454>

Filgona, J., Sakiyo, J., Gwany, D. M., & Okoronka, A. U. (2020). Motivation in learning. *Asian Journal of Education and social studies*,

10(4), 16-37. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajess/2020/v10i430273>

Gheitasi, M., Moreno, J. A., Hermon, S., & Schnabel, M. A. (2023). Gaming the Past– Commercial Video Games with historical contexts: Evaluation of the Iranian Lotf Ali Khan Game. *JGGAG (Journal of Games, Game Art, and Gamification)*, 8(1), 24–36. <https://doi.org/10.21512/jggag.v8i1.9874>

Gomez, J., Dumon, J. M., Trasmonte, E., Carreon, L., & Cabello, C. (2024). Desirable or Undesirable: Attitude and Behavior of Students toward Transitioning from Online to Face-to-Face Mode of Learning. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 21(2), 207-217.

Gultom, S., Hutauruk, A. F., & Ginting, A. M. (2020). Teaching skills of teacher in increasing student learning interest. *Budapest International Research and Critics Institute Journal (BIRCI-Journal)*, 3(3), 1564–1569. <https://doi.org/10.33258/birci.v3i3.1086>

Haniah, A. R., Aman, A., & Setiawan, R. (2020). Integration of strengthening of character education and higher order thinking skills in history learning. *Journal of Education and Learning (Edisi Elektronik)/Journal of Education and Learning*, 14(2), 183–190. <https://doi.org/10.11591/edulearn.v14i2.15010>

Issar, K. (2021). Students’ attitude towards studying history and teaching practices. *Education Quarterly Reviews*, 4(3), 2621-5799. <https://doi.org/10.31014/aior.1993.04.03.316>

Jaicten, A. R., Uzarraga, A. R., Rodriguez, R., & Cabello, C. (2023). A Review of Stories Untold in Modular Distance Learning: A Phenomenology. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 12(3), 230-237.

Jamiludin, J., & Darnawati, D. (2022). E-learning on History learning: Aspect of material, teacher, learning environment, and student. *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education*, 11(2), 546. <https://doi.org/10.11591/ijere.v11i2.22471>

Kali, Y., Sagy, O., Benichou, M., Atias, O., & Levin-Peled, R. (2019). Teaching expertise reconsidered: The technology, pedagogy, content and space (TPeCS) knowledge framework. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 50(5), 2162–2177. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjet.12847>

Kisida, B., Goodwin, L., & Bowen, D. H. (2020). Teaching History Through Theater: The Effects of Arts Integration on Students’ Knowledge and Attitudes. *AERA Open*, 6(1), 233285842090271. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2332858420902712>

Koné, K. (2021). Exploring the impact of performance-based assessment on Malian EFL learners’ motivation. *Advances in Language and Literary Studies*, 12(3), 51–64. <https://doi.org/10.7575/aiac.all.v.12n.3.p>

Kusuma, G. P., Suryapranata, L. K. P., Wigati, E. K., & Utomo, Y. (2021). Enhancing historical learning using Role-Playing Game on mobile platform. *Procedia Computer Science*, 179, 886–893. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2021.01.078>

Leal-Rodriguez, A. L., & Albort-Morant, G. (2019). Promoting innovative experiential learning practices to improve academic performance: Empirical evidence from a Spanish Business School. *Journal of Innovation & Knowledge*, 4(2), 97–103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jik.2017.12.001>

Lesh, B. (2023). “Why won’t you just tell us the answer?” <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781032683164>

Malazonia, D., Macharashvili, T., Maglakelidze, S., & Chiabrishvili, N. (2021). Developing students’ intercultural values and attitudes through history education in monocultural school environments (Georgian-language school case study). *Intercultural Education*, 32(5), 508–524. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14675986.2021.1966267>

Malm, B. (2020). On the complexities of educating student teachers: teacher educators’ views on contemporary challenges to their profession. *JET. Journal of Education For Teaching/Journal of Education For Teaching*, 46(3), 351–364. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02607476.2020.1739514>

McGregor, H. E., Pind, J., & Karn, S. (2021). A ‘wicked problem’: rethinking history education in the Anthropocene. *Rethinking History*, 25(4), 483–507. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13642529.2021.1992159>

Miftakhu Rosyad, A. ., Sudrajat, J., & Heng Loke, S. (2022). Role of Social Studies Teacher to Inculcate Student Character Values. *International Journal of Science Education and Cultural Studies*, 1(1), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.58291/ijsecs.v1i1.20>

Monteiro, V., Carvalho, C., & Santos, N. N. (2021a). Creating a supportive classroom environment through effective feedback: effects on students’ school identification and behavioral engagement. *Frontiers in Education*, 6. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2021.661736>

Moreno-Guerrero, A. J., Rodríguez-Jiménez, C., Gómez-García, G., & Navas-Parejo, M. R. (2020). Educational Innovation in Higher Education: Use of role playing and educational video in future teachers’ training. *Sustainability*, 12(6), 2558. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12062558>

Munna, A. S., & Kalam, M. A. (2021). Teaching and learning process to enhance teaching effectiveness: literature review. *IJHI (International Journal of Humanities and Innovation)*, 4(1), 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.33750/ijhi.v4i1.102>

Murray, J. (2019). Hearing young children’s voices. *International Journal of Early Years Education*, 27(1), 1–5.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/09669760.2018.1563352>

Ogang, C. J. E., Balbuena, J., Tabanao, K. M., Amante, W. M., Sambrana, M. G., Bandoquillo, H. M., ... & Minyamin, A. (2022). The Freshmen and their Fresh Start: A Phenomenology. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 2(6), 541-551.

Papadatou-Pastou, M., Touloumakos, A. K., Koutouveli, C., & Barrable, A. (2020). The learning styles neuromyth: when the same term means different things to different teachers. *European Journal of Psychology of Education*, 36(2), 511-531. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10212-020-00485-2>

Pedersen, S., & Hoby, M. (2020). Implications of Assessing Student-Driven Projects: A case study of possible challenges and an argument for reflexivity. *Education Sciences*, 10(1), 19. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci10010019>

Perez, Z. O., Minyamin, A. V., Bagsit, R. D., Gimena, G. B., Dionaldo, W. V., Padillo, E. S., ... & Cabello, C. A. (2022). Research capability of faculty members in higher education institution: Basis for research management plan. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 6(3), 6215-6226.

Popa, N. (2021). Operationalizing Historical Consciousness: A review and synthesis of the literature on meaning making in historical learning. *Review of Educational Research*, 92(2), 171-208. <https://doi.org/10.3102/00346543211052333>

Rajačić, A. B., Kišjuhas, A., & Škoric, M. (2020). The Sociology of Gossip and Small Talk: A Metatheory. *SociolóGia*, 52(6), 559-577. <https://doi.org/10.31577/sociologia.2020.52.6.23>

Riconalla, P. G., Quiñanola, K. K., Devila, J., Zozobrado, J., Estoque, R. M., Capito, N., ... & Minyamin, A. (2022). The Lived Experiences Aged Instructors in Online Classes: Their Struggles and Coping Mechanisms. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 3(1), 1-11.

Sailer, M., Stadler, M., Schultz-Pernice, F., Franke, U., Schöffmann, C., Paniotova, V., Husagic, L., & Fischer, F. (2021). Technology-related teaching skills and attitudes: Validation of a scenario-based self-assessment instrument for teachers. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 115, Article 106625. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2020.106625>

Salehi, H., & Kiani, S. (2021). Vocabulary Recall Improvement through Acronyms: A Case Study of Iranian Advanced EFL Learners. *International Journal of Language and Translation Research*, 1(3), 1-14. https://doi.org/10.12906/978389966737_001

Schmidt, S. J. (2020). Distracted learning: Big problem and golden opportunity. *Journal of Food Science Education*, 19(4), 278-291. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1541-4329.12206>

Sebbowa, D. K., & Ng'ambi, D. (2020). Teaching History in Ways C21St Students Learn – A Design-Based Research Perspective. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research/International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 19(9), 259-280. <https://doi.org/10.26803/ijlter.19.9.14>

Şenşekerci, E., Sari, M (2019). The Awareness, Attitude, and Opinions of Social Studies Teachers Regarding The Use of Movies And Serials In Teaching History Subjects. *European Journal of Education Studies*, 6(4), 291-316. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.3349992

Solé, M. G. P. S. (2019). Children's understanding of time: A study in a primary history classroom. *History Education Research Journal*, 16(1). <https://doi.org/10.18546/herj.16.1.13>

Suswandari, S., Absor, N. F., & Soleh, M. B. (2021). Meme as a History Learning Media in The Post-Millennial Generation. *Paramita/Paramita: Historical Studies Journal*, 31(2). <https://doi.org/10.15294/paramita.v31i2.26854>

Sutton, D. E. (2020). *Memories cast in stone*. In Routledge eBooks. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003086079>

Thompson, D. C. (2021). Some psychological aspects of history teaching. In Routledge eBooks (pp. 18-38). <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781032163840-3>

Thorp, R., & Persson, A. (2020). On historical thinking and the history educational challenge. *Educational Philosophy and Theory*, 52(8), 891-901. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131857.2020.1712550>

Triana, D., & Sari, M. F. (2023). THE EFFECT OF GLOBALIZATION ON EXISTENCE REGIONAL CULTURE. *journal.berpusi.co.id*. <https://doi.org/10.62966/ijose.v1i2.106>

Van Ditmarsch, H., Van Der Hoek, W., & Kuijer, L. B. (2020). The logic of gossiping. *Artificial Intelligence*, 286, 103306. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.artint.2020.103306>

Van Straaten, D., Wilschut, A., & Oostdam, R. (2018). Connecting past and present through case-comparison learning in history: views of teachers and students. *Journal of Curriculum Studies*, 51(5), 643-663. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220272.2018.1558457>

Vantieghem, W., Roose, I., Gheysens, E., Griful-Freixenet, J., Keppens, K., Vanderlinde, R., Struyven, K., & Van Avermaet, P. (2020). Professional vision of inclusive classrooms: A validation of teachers' reasoning on differentiated instruction and teacher-student interactions. *Studies in Educational Evaluation*, 67, 100912. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.stueduc.2020.100912>

Verburgt, L. M. (2020). The history of knowledge and the future history of ignorance. *Know*, 4(1), 1-24.

<https://doi.org/10.1086/708341>

Walsh, T., Henderson, M. (2022). The Impact of Video in the K-12 Classroom: A scoping study of instructional video research. Monash University. Report. <https://doi.org/10.26180/19614093>.

Wu, X., Zhang, L. J., & Liu, Q. (2021b). Using Assessment for Learning: Multi-Case studies of three Chinese university English as a Foreign Language (EFL) teachers engaging students in learning and assessment. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.725132>

Wuryandani, W & Herwin. (2021). The effect of the think pair share model on learning outcomes of Civics in elementary school students. *Cypriot Journal of Educational Science*. 16(2), 627-640. <https://doi.org/10.18844/cjes.v16i2.5640>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Claire June Z. Quiñanola

Cebu Technological University – Philippines

Nathalie Jean T. Templado

Cebu Technological University – Philippines

Ritchel Marie B. Sabanal

Cebu Technological University – Philippines

Glicel D. Ugbamen

Cebu Technological University – Philippines

Sharlette Mae R. Ditan

Cebu Technological University – Philippines

Ranie Rose F. Gabutero

Cebu Technological University – Philippines

Lalyn M. Amolo

Cebu Technological University – Philippines

Krizamaine Y. Domugho

Cebu Technological University – Philippines

Jelly Mañen G. Osorio

Cebu Technological University – Philippines

Jacky Lou V. Medillo

Cebu Technological University – Philippines

Riscelle A. Mirafuentes

Cebu Technological University – Philippines

Glaiza Jane R. Magallanes

Cebu Technological University – Philippines

Jerame E. Landiza

Cebu Technological University – Philippines

Justine Serato

Cebu Technological University – Philippines

Jolimar S. Sy

Cebu Technological University – Philippines

Cyril A. Cabello, PhD

Cebu Technological University – Philippines